

HERBAL DRUGS WITH CARDIOTONIC EFFECTS

Ratsa V.,*Assistant Department of Internal Medicine
Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi***Nadiia Lazaruk,***4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Yuliia Bobrynets,***4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Berezovska Inna***4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Abstract**

The problem of cardiovascular diseases is becoming more and more urgent. The mortality statistics from this group of diseases is increasing every day. At the same time, the therapeutic approach to the treatment of cardiac diseases is improved by the modernization of technologies. But among all drugs, the leading place will always be taken by herbal drugs. Among the population of our country, phytodrugs [1], which are perceived by patients as safer compared to chemically synthesized medicinal products, are more trusted.

Keywords: ischemic heart disease, cardiac glycosides, phytodrugs, cardiotoxic effect, plant origin.

Introduction

Cardiotonic agents are drugs that increase the contractile activity of the myocardium and normalize the functions of the heart. These drugs are divided into two groups: cardiac glycosides and drugs of "non-glycoside" nature [2]. More than 2000 plants are included in the traditional (herbal/alternative) system of medicine, and some of them are recommended for therapeutic purposes in patients suffering from cardiovascular diseases, especially in conditions such as "hyperlipidemia" and "ischemic heart disease" [3]. It is known that many herbs containing cardiac glycosides also contain digoxin-like substances, including milkweed, lily of the valley, Siberian ginseng, and hawthorne berries [4, 5].

Materials and methods.

In order to reveal the topic in full, we reviewed a variety of freely available literature. Each of the sources was examined and elaborated in detail.

All sources were taken from open access libraries, namely PubMed, Cochrane, ScienceDirect, The Lancet, etc.

Research results

One of the leading diseases causing morbidity and mortality are cardiovascular diseases. There is a strong global trend towards a revival of interest in the traditional system of medicine. At the same time, unofficial statistical data indicate that a number of herbal products are traditionally used by doctors for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases [6].

Because plants have always been a rich source of active metabolites against many diseases, where cardiovascular disease (CVD) has been one of the most important health problems worldwide [7].

More than 12 million patients of Ukraine suffer from cardiovascular diseases [8], therefore medicinal preparations of herbal origin are very relevant, because they not only have a positive therapeutic effect, but are also economically beneficial.

In blood plasma, cardiac glycosides form complexes with albumins. As the polarity of cardiac glycosides decreases, their bond with proteins becomes stronger. The amount of cardiac glycosides not bound

to proteins increases with hypoproteinemia, the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, anticoagulants, and prolonged sulfonamides.

There are a lot of herbal drugs with cardiotoxic effects registered in Ukraine, for example, digitoxin (*Digitalis purpurea*), digoxin, celanide (*Digitalis lanata*), digalen-neo (*Digitalis ferruginea*), strophanthin K (*Strophantus Kombe*), strophanthin G (*Strophantus gratus*), corglycone (*Convallaria*), adoniside herbal infusion, extract (*Adonis vernalis*).

According to the pharmacokinetic properties, three groups of cardiac glycosides are distinguished:

- drugs with a quick and relatively short-term effect and with a slight ability to accumulate - strophanthin, corglycon;
- glycosides with an average rate of development of the effect, its average duration and moderate ability to accumulate - digoxin, celanide;
- glycosides with a slow development of the effect and its significant duration and pronounced ability to cumulate - digitoxin.

There is also a study that claims *Terminalia arjuna* bark extract has a cardiotoxic effect on adult ventricular myocytes [9].

A literature review [9] states that *Terminalia arjuna* is an ayurvedic cardioactive herbal product with known organic components including tannins, triterpenoid saponins (eg, arjunic acid and its derivatives), flavonoids, gallic acid, ellagic acid, oligomeric proanthocyanidins, and phytosterols. It is also described that the bark of *Terminalia arjuna* mainly has a cardiotoxic effect and is used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various cardiovascular diseases. Studies in animal models have shown that organic extracts of *Terminalia arjuna* bark reduce blood pressure and heart rate, and counteract the effects of norepinephrine and isoproterenol (ISO) and myocardial ischemia.

Cardiac glycosides (glycoside, steroid cardiotoxic agents) are complex nitrogen-free substances of plant origin that have a selective direct cardiotoxic effect. Steroidal cardiotoxic substances have also been iso-

lated from the skin of amphibians. Semisynthetic cardiac glycosides (methylazide, acetyldigoxin, etc.) are also used in clinical practice.

While using cardiac glycosides, ATP energy is used more productively. An increase in the number of Ca^{2+} ions in the diastole phase helps to maintain the tone of the heart muscle, that is, a positive inotropic effect is manifested. The positive therapeutic effect of cardiac glycosides is due to the inhibition of Na^+ , K^+ -ATPase by approximately 35%, when the inhibitory effect of the drugs decreases, the effect disappears, and when the activity of the enzyme is inhibited by more than 60%, toxic effects develop [2].

The positive effect of cardiac glycosides is manifested in the form of an increase in the rate of development of myocardial tension, the magnitude and speed of muscle contractions, and an increase in stroke volume. All phases of systole become shorter. The amount of residual blood in the ventricular cavities decreases. Elevation of the R wave, narrowing of the QRS complex, lowering of the S-T segment below the isoelectric line, flattening or inversion of the T wave are observed on the electrocardiogram [2].

In this review, we want to describe in more detail one of the drugs that has a cardiotonic effect, which is quite popular in use in Ukraine.

Corglyconum is a drug registered in Ukraine C01A X04** Preparations of lily of the valley, active ingredient: CONVALLARIA MAJALIS. This drug is indicated for acute and chronic heart failure (with intolerance to digitalis drugs). Corglycon is a mixture Convallaria glycosides. The main pharmacodynamic effects of corglycon are positive inotropic, negative dromotropic and chronotropic effects. Cardiac glycosides increase the systolic contraction of the heart, prolong the diastole, slow down the heart rhythm, and reduce the excitability of the heart's conduction system. Strengthening the contraction of the myocardium significantly improves blood circulation. The mechanism of action of corglycon on the heart is associated with stimulation of the sodium-potassium pump and an increase in the level of catecholamines in the myocardium, which causes a positive inotropic effect. In addition, under the influence of corglycon, the activity of phosphodiesterase decreases, which leads to an increase in cyclic adenosine monophosphate.

Corglycon is subject to biotransformation in the liver, but its removal from the body may change in case of impaired biliary function: in such cases, the excretion of corglycon with urine increases. Accumulation of the drug can occur only with a combination of serious disorders of biliary and urinary excretion in the body of a patient with heart failure. The pharmacological effect develops after 3 - 5 minutes after intravenous administration of the drug, the maximum effect is noted after 25 - 30 minutes.

The drug is also indicated for the tachysystolic form of atrial fibrillation, for the treatment of supraventricular paroxysmal tachycardia.

There are also certain caveats in use. When symptoms of overdose appear, the glycoside is discontinued. Another cardiotonic agent is prescribed instead. For ex-

ample, dopamine or dobutamine. It is necessary to prescribe drugs that bind glycosides and reduce their circulation in the blood. These can be drugs that reduce the flow of cardiac glycosides from the gastrointestinal tract into the blood: tannin, cholestyramine, activated carbon, laxatives. They are prescribed regardless of the route of administration of cardiotonic drugs, since cardiac glycosides undergo enterohepatic circulation. To eliminate hypokalemia, potassium preparations are prescribed - potassium chloride inside or intravenous drip, a polarizing mixture (10% potassium chloride solution 20 ml, 5 units of insulin and 5% glucose solution 400 ml). Potassium preparations are used to prevent the toxic effect of glycosides on the heart, especially disturbances in the rhythm of heart contractions. For the same purpose, magnesium preparations are shown - magnesium sulfate or combined preparations of potassium and magnesium - panangin, asparkam (containing potassium and magnesium asparaginate).

Pathogenetically justified is the use of donors of sulfhydryl groups and sulfate-containing derivatives of amino acids, such as upitil, taurium, cysteine, methionine, acetylcysteine. The most effective remedy is unithiol (1 ml of 5% solution per 10 kg of the patient's body weight 2-3 times intramuscularly in the first 2 days of treatment, and then once a day).

The mechanism of the antidote action of unithiol and other thiol compounds is related to their ability to reduce the toxic effect of glycosides on the functional activity of compounds containing SH-groups, proteins (enzymes), including ATPase, and to normalize indicators of energy metabolism of the myocardium. The positive aspects of the pharmacodynamics of unithiol are insignificant toxicity, it is well tolerated by patients, it does not affect the cardiotonic properties of cardiac glycosides.

Conclusion. Based on the research, we can say that there is a rather small number of studies on drugs based on plant raw materials, because despite the positive effect of these drugs, physicians of evidence-based medicine do not refer this group of drugs to traditional methods of treatment.

References

1. Людмила Онишук - Як оптимізувати комплексне лікування пацієнтів з шемічною хворобою серця? КАРДІОЛОГІЯ АСПЕКТИ ЛІКУВАННЯ/ www.health-ua.com
2. Фармакологія лікарських засобів, що впливають на серцево-судинну систему : навч. посіб. / І. Ю. Висоцький, Н. В. Глущенко, Р. А. Храмова. – Суми : Сумський державний університет, 2016. – 158 с. ISBN 978-966-657-645-6.
3. Mahmood ZA, Sualeh M, Mahmood SB, Karim MA. Herbal treatment for cardiovascular disease the evidence based therapy. Pak J Pharm Sci. 2010 Jan;23(1):119-24. PMID: 20067878.
4. Cheng TO. Interaction of herbal drugs with digoxin. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2002 Aug 21;40(4):838-9. doi: 10.1016/s0735-1097(02)02022-3. PMID: 12204525.
5. L.G. Miller. Herbal medicinals: selected clinical considerations focusing on known or potential

drug-herb interactions. Arch Intern Med, 158 (1998), pp. 2200-2211

6. Adome RO, Gachihi JW, Onegi B, Tamale J, Apio SO. The cardiotoxic effect of the crude ethanolic extract of Nerium oleander in the isolated guinea pig hearts. Afr Health Sci. 2003 Aug;3(2):77-82. PMID: 12913798; PMCID: PMC2141602.

7. Orhan IE, Gokbulut A, Senol FS. Adonis sp., Convallaria sp., Strophanthus sp., Thevetia sp., and Leonurus sp. - Cardiotoxic Plants with Known Traditional Use and a Few Preclinical and Clinical Studies. Curr Pharm Des. 2017;23(7):1051-1059. doi: 10.2174/1381612822666161010104548. PMID: 27748195.

8. O. S. Kukhtenko, L. S. Simonyan, Ye. V. Hladukh Market research of medicinal products which are used in cardiological diseases treatment. Current issues in pharmacy and medicine: science and practice 2017; 10 (2), 219–223. UDC: 614.272:615.22:616.12-009. DOI: 10.14739/2409-2932.2017.2.103783

9. Oberoi L, Akiyama T, Lee KH, Liu SJ. The aqueous extract, not organic extracts, of Terminalia arjuna bark exerts cardiotoxic effect on adult ventricular myocytes. Phytomedicine. 2011 Feb 15;18(4):259-65. doi: 10.1016/j.phymed.2010.07.006. PMID: 21315570.

NEPHROPROTECTORS WITH PLANT ORIGIN

Ratsa V.,

*Assistant Department of Internal Medicine
Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi*

Holodniak Yu.,

4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Navrotska D.

4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Cheipesh M.

4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Abstract

In this research, we want to reveal the issue of nephroprotectors with plant origin and their importance in treatment of acute kidney injury. It is known that acute kidney injury (AKI) can occur in nearly 20–200 per million population in the community. It is important to know that AKI is associated with morbidity and mortality; every year almost 2 million people worldwide die of AKI, whereas AKI survivors are at high risk of developing chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end-stage renal disease (ESRD) — conditions that carry a high burden. By the way, many plants have been well recognized for their nephroprotective properties. Moreover, they have a wide range of pharmacological effects, the most significant of which are antioxidant, antihypoxic, angioprotective, membrane-stabilizing and anti-inflammatory, that can help in solving this issue.

Keywords: acute kidney injury, nephroprotectors, flavonoids, drugs with plant origin, antioxidants.

Introduction

It is important to note that researchers say that by 2040, kidney disease could become the fifth leading cause of death among all diseases in the world. Kidney damage can be caused by some pre-, intra- and postrenal factors. Diabetes, liver diseases, rhabdomyolysis, and intestinal microbiota are among the prerenal factors. Regarding postrenal factors, such diseases as lithiasis or blood clots in the ureters, prostate cancer, urethral obstruction, prostate enlargement and urinary tract infections can be distinguished. Also, it is important do not forget about the nephrotoxicity of drugs, they can also cause severe kidney damage. As well, there is such a thing as the nephrotoxicity of drugs, they can also cause severe kidney damage. Therefore, it should be noted that we must supplement the treatment with drugs that protect the kidneys, namely nephroprotectors [1].

Materials and methods.

Various scientific materials were used during the execution of this work, namely articles by modern researchers, which fully cover this topic.

The research was carried out in various services, namely PubMed, Cochrane, The Lancet, etc.

Research results

Over the last decades, a lot of research has been carried out, which allows us to learn more about acute kidney injury, as well as to improve diagnosis in the early stages. Consensus definitions were therefore created in 2012 and finally unified by the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) group [2].

Treatment standards are constantly changing to influence patient survival; but even so, mortality in severe APF remains very high despite several improvements in treatment.

In order to better understand the importance of nephroprotectors, it is important to understand why some drugs are nephrotoxic. For example, consider such a drug as Gentamicin.

Gentamicin, a strong cationic drug which precipitates acute nephrotoxicity, because of accumulation at biological membranes and causes net increase in oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation leading to necrotic changes in renal tubules [3].

There are studies where described that there are several phytoconstituents and plants extracts demonstrated significant anti-oxidant and cyto-protective activities. Vitex negundo Linn. (VN), Oroxyllum indicum